

Training food researchers in open science: A series of interactive workshops.

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ABSTRACT

A train-the-trainer program was organized and focused on introducing open science principles and practices and the use of FNS-Cloud. Three series of interactive workshops on open science took place from April 2021 and July 2023. Attendance was mostly food science technologists and nutritionists due to the nature of FNS-Cloud project. The series of workshops in 2021 showed that more than 80% of participants produced research data, and almost 29% had searched for data in an open repository, however only 17% had uploaded data to an open repository. Most participants had positive comments when asked “What comes to your mind with open science, open data, open publishing?” but the biggest obstacle to making data open was identified as being their lack of understanding. The overall ratings of the workshops were mostly very and extremely helpful (82-90%) and the favorite parts of participants were the interactive activities, discussions, role-playing exercises, and hands-on activities. Participants feedback reflected that they were motivated to learn more about open science and FNS-Cloud and teach others about what they have learned.

Keywords: Open data, repositories, FNS-Cloud, train-the-trainer

INTRODUCTION

Open Science is a system change allowing for better science. It is based on transparent and collaborative ways of producing and sharing knowledge and data as early as possible in the research process, and for communicating and sharing results (European Commission, 2019). In this context, the Food Nutrition Security Cloud project (FNS-Cloud, H2020 No. 863059) aimed to develop an infrastructure, tools, and services to exploit food, nutrition, and security data as a way to make food science less fragmented and more open.

Training in specific skills and capabilities is widely recognized to help organizations achieve their goals and create competitive advantage by adding value to their key resources – i.e., employees (Nikandrou et al., 2009). To give support to the users of the FNS-Cloud infrastructure, a train-the-trainer program was organized and focused on introducing open science principles and practices and the use of cloud catalogs, tools, and services available within the FNS-Cloud project. The training program was designed based on the outcomes of interviews to the project researchers, where discussions covered what they wanted to learn, how they preferred to learn, and who are their ideal trainers (Flynn et al. 2022).

One of the main challenges to run an open science training program is a general reluctance of researchers to adopt open science best practices, mainly because of lack of awareness but even acknowledging their benefits (Köster et al, 2021). This concern led to the training developers to choose interactive workshops as the learning methodology for the program. Interactive workshops involve a collection of activities that are organized for groups of participants who must work together to explore and solve problems presented to them collectively. These activities include small-group discussions, scenarios, simulation, videos, games, and role plays. Interactive workshops are conducted over a specific period and in a certain location (Mukurunge et al., 2021). The number of participants in an interactive workshop should not exceed 15, to allow every participant to actively engage with the study material (Elliot et al., 2016). In interactive workshops, small-group discussions enhance the building up of trust and confidence and sharing of ideas amongst participants in a non-judgmental environment (Dorri et al., 2019).

The aim of this work is to assess the performance of the three series of interactive workshops on open science that constituted the FNS-Cloud train-the-trainer program.

METHODS

Workshops

Thirteen train-the-trainer workshops took place between April 2021 and July 2023 as part of the FNS-Cloud project. These workshops were organized under three Open Science-related titles which increased in specificity as the FNS-Cloud project progressed (Table 1). The workshops were developed and delivered by a team of food science researchers at the following four organizations: EFFoST (European Federation of Food Science and Technology), EuroFIR (European Food Information Resource), ILSI-Europe (International Life Sciences Institute-Europe), and ISEKI-Food Association (Integrating Science and Engineering Knowledge into Food). Workshops were free of charge and although officially open to anyone they were geared

towards food science researchers from universities or research organizations. Workshops were given several times, always associated with a major food-related event or conference and in some cases registration at the event was required, e.g., at the EFFoST Annual Conferences of 2021 and 2022, or at the FNS-Cloud project meetings of 2022 and 2023. Number of attendees was recorded for all workshops except those associated with FNS-Cloud project meetings where numbers are estimated based on project meeting attendance. Workshops were approximately two hours in length and were delivered either online, face-to-face, or hybrid.

Table 1. Workshops were associated with events and delivered in different formats.

Workshop title (year)	Associated events	Delivery
An Open Science Taster (2021)	EuroFIR Food Forum ISEKI-Food Conference ILSI-Europe Annual Meeting BOKU Food Technology Webinars EFFoST Annual Conference	Online Online Online Online Face-to-Face
Upload your Scientific Work to an Open Repository (2022)	EuroFIR Food Forum ILSI-Europe Annual Meeting ISEKI-Food Webinar FNS-Cloud Project Meeting EFFoST Annual Conference	Hybrid Online Online Face-to-Face Face-to-Face
A Researcher's Journey through the FNSCloud (2023)	FNS-Cloud Project Meeting EuroFIR Food Forum ISEKI-Food Conference	Face-to-Face Hybrid Face-to-Face

Each workshop title covered several topics (Table 2). Workshop titles and topics were decided by the workshop facilitators based on a series of consultations with participants in the FNS-Cloud project (Flynn et al., 2022). Attendance was limited to a maximum of 15 due to the interactive nature of the workshops in which participants were asked to provide input by i) reflect silently and provide open text responses to questions, ii) discuss or role play in small groups and provide open text responses to questions, and/or iii) vote yes or no to specific questions. Participants also performed specific hands-on activities with open science tools, in which no questions were posed. At the end of each workshop, all participants were asked to complete the same workshop evaluation (Annex 1). Publicity for all workshops was through Social Media channels of the FNS-Cloud project and the four organizing institutes and included text information, short videos, and short articles in institute newsletters. A certificate of completion was given to all who successfully completed a workshop and its corresponding evaluation form.

Table 2. FNS-Cloud train-the-trainer workshop series covered aspects of open science with a variety of participant activities.

Workshop title (year)	Topics	Participant activities (no. of questions posed)
An Open Science Taster (2021)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thinking about Open Science 2. Open Data 3. Open Publishing 4. Open Science Communication 5. Resources: EOOSC and FNS-Cloud 	In-workshop: Yes/No vote (3) Open ended (3) Role play (0) Discussions (0) Post-workshop: Likert scale (4) Open ended (3)
Upload your Scientific Work to an Open Repository (2022)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The basics of making your scientific work Open and FAIR and teach this to your team 2. Upload your scientific work to an open repository and teach your team to do the same 3. Publicize, advertise, and raise awareness about your scientific work and teach your team to do the same 	In-workshop: Open ended (5) Hands-on activity (0) Discussions (0) Post-workshop: Likert scale (4) Open ended (3)
A Researcher's Journey through the FNSCloud (2023)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduction to the FNSCloud and the Food Intake researcher's journey 2. Food Traceability database search engine hands-on activity 3. Exploitation of food composition and labeling data 4. How to use FAIRSPACE: The Microbiome Demonstrator 	In-workshop: Hands-on activity (0) Post-workshop: Likert scale (4) Open ended (3)

Qualitative and quantitative questions were posed to participants during the workshops and answers were anonymous i.e., these data were not linked to a specific workshop participant. Questions were answered in Padlet or VoxVote during online workshops and on sticky notes in person. The number and type of in-workshop activities which generated data varied depending on the workshop title, from three quantitative and three qualitative questions in the 2021 workshops to seven qualitative questions in 2022 to no data-generating in-workshop questions in 2023.

The post-workshop evaluation was the same for all participants in all years and it contained four quantitative and three qualitative questions (Annex 1). The evaluation was in Survey Monkey and

available immediately after the workshop by following a QR code. In the days after the workshop participants received an email reminder to complete the post-workshop evaluation. Apart from the first 2021 workshop “Open Science Taster” at EuroFIR Food Forum, participants were required to complete the post-workshop evaluation in order to receive a certificate for completion of the workshop. The evaluations were anonymous.

Quantitative data collection and analysis

For the three quantitative in-workshop questions in the 2021 Open Science Taster workshops, participants had 1 minute each to answer Yes or No to the following:

1. Have you ever produced research data?
2. Have you ever searched for data in an open data repository?
3. Have you ever uploaded data to an open data repository?

In three quantitative post-workshop questions, participants answered the following using a Likert scale of 1 to 5 where 1 indicated poor quality or strong disagreement and 5 indicated high quality or strong agreement.

1. How would you rate the workshop overall?
2. My basic knowledge of Open Science/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS-Cloud before the Workshop was satisfactory.
3. My basic knowledge of Open Science/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS-Cloud after the Workshop is satisfactory.

One post-workshop question gave three choices:

1. I found the workshop length (2h) i) too long ii) just about right iii) too short

Answers to each quantitative question were combined and summed for all workshops. For the three in-workshop Yes/No questions.

Qualitative data collection and analysis

For the eight in-workshop qualitative open-ended questions, responses were downloaded as excel files or transcribed into excel and checked by up to three researchers. Unclear responses were reviewed and, following agreement of two of three researchers, updated to improve understanding, spelling and/or grammar. Qualitative questions were as follows:

In the 2021 workshop series:

1. “Write any short topic, idea, tool or concept that you associate with these terms: Open Data, Open Publishing, and Open Science Communication.”
2. “What is the single biggest obstacle to making your data open?”
3. “What are the most important aspects of open science to communicate to your close colleagues? How would you share these aspects with your colleagues?”

In the 2022 workshop series:

1. “What comes to mind when you hear “Open Science?”
2. “Can you name an open science repository?”

3. “What would you write in a Tweet about the topic we just covered? Or “What have you learned that you would teach others?”. This question was asked three times, once after each workshop topic.
4. “List the metadata you consider important to find the following items: a conference presentation, a diagram, a LinkedIn post.”
5. Put together a strategy to promote your work: 1) What is your goal? 2) Who do you want to reach? Who is your target audience? 3) Which channels are most suitable to promote your work?

In the post-workshop evaluation:

1. What is your professional area of expertise?
2. What was your favorite part of the workshop?
3. If you were to organize the next "Open Science Taster/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS Cloud" Workshop, what would you do differently?

Inductive coding (Chandra & Sang, 2019) of participant responses was done in excel or with the NVivo 12 Pro© software for qualitative analysis, following an iterative approach involving up to three researchers reviewing responses, codes, sub-codes, and coded phrases. Following inductive coding, comparisons of the number of comments assigned to each code were displayed either i) graphically, ii) in word clouds using words of at least four letters and grouping by synonyms, or iii) with area-based hierarchical tree maps. Representative words and phrases were chosen by at least two researchers to illustrate certain questions.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Workshop purpose and attendance

“An Open Science Taster” was the first workshop introducing the pillars of Open Science and focused on (1) definitions and components (2) advantages of opening research, and (3) challenges in Open Science (Table 2). The second workshop, “Uploading your Scientific Work to an Open Repository”, focused on (1) definition and importance of Open Science, (2) open repositories, (3) uploading a scientific work on Zenodo, and (4) importance of maximizing research impact (Table 2). These two workshops were presented by four European hubs, based in BE, NL and AT, at five events (Table 1) and the aim was to empower user communities and promote improved professional practice, increased awareness of the benefits of open science, and exploitation of food research data resources.

The third and last workshop “A Researcher’s Journey through the FNSCloud” presented the FNS-Cloud to the community and focused on (1) introduction of FNS-Cloud and its importance to FAIR data and research impact and (2) use of the FNS tools in selected case studies. This workshop aimed to share results of the FNS-Cloud HORIZON 2020 project and how to use them; it was performed three times (Table 1) by the same European hubs as the first two workshops.

Workshop attendance ranged from 42 to 57 (Table 3), with people at online and hybrid workshops not always remaining for the full workshop and not all attendees completing all in-workshop

activities. The post-workshop evaluation was completed by almost 50% of attendees, ranging from a low of 40% in 2023 to a high of 49% in 2022.

Attendees self-identified their professional area of expertise, and three researchers independently assigned these identifications to either Food Science & Technology, Nutrition, both or Other. On average, 47% of attendees at the 2021 and 2022 workshops, i.e. “An Open Science Taster” and “Uploading your Scientific Work to an Open Repository” were included in the professional expertise as Food Science & Technology, while in 2023, “A Researcher’s Journey through the FNSSCloud” less than 20% of attendees were Food Scientists & Technologists and more than 40% were neither Food Scientists & Technologists nor Nutritionists (Figure 1). This change in the profile of workshop attendees suggests that the final workshop was of interest to a more varied audience, possibly due to the increased awareness of Open Science throughout all scientific disciplines in the three years that these workshops took place.

Table 3. Workshop title, year performed, number of participants and evaluations.

Title	Year	Participants	Evaluations
An Open Science Taster	2021	57	26
Upload your Scientific Work to an Open Repository	2022	47	23
A Researcher’s Journey through the FNSSCloud	2023	42	17
	Total	146	66

Workshop content: questions and activities

“An Open Science Taster” (Workshop 2021) and “Uploading your Scientific Work to an Open Repository” (Workshop 2022) contained 6 and 9 activities, respectively. In the Workshop 2021, there was 1 voting activity, 4 open questions and 2 brainstorming activities while in the workshop 2022, there were 3 open questions and 4 hands-on activities.

The Workshop 2021 voting showed that more than 80% of participants produced research data, and almost 29% had searched for data in an open repository, however only 17% had uploaded data to an open repository (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Area of professional expertise of workshop participants (%). Workshop 2021 (n=26), Workshop 2022 (n= 23), Workshop 2023 (n=17).

Figure 2. Voting activity results from the “Open Science Taster” workshops. “Have you ever produced research data?” (n=32), “Have you ever uploaded to an open data repository?” (n=35), “Have you ever searched in an open data repository?” (n=35).

The 2021 and 2022 workshops had several open-ended questions in which the number of responses varied since not all participants answered all questions and some questions allowed more than one answer. These brainstorming and hands-on activities were related to the specific workshop topic and allowed the participants to think and delve into deep discussion about the topic as well as to have hands-on practice, particularly in the case of the 2022 workshop “Uploading your Scientific Work to an Open Repository”. The open-ended questions used in these workshops are grouped into two categories: (1) What participants know about the topic (Figure 3, 4, 5) and (2) What participants find important about the topic (Figure 6).

In the first category is the question “What comes to your mind with open science, open data, open publishing?” Here, 125 comments came from the participants of both workshops. More than 75% of these had some positive component, 14% negative, and the remainder neutral (Figure 3). Some comments were categorized as both positive and negative: “publications that are free to read but not necessarily free to publish unfortunately”.

Both positive and negative comments often specified open publications and/or open data: On the positive side publications and data were equally mentioned, each about 6% of all positive comments, while on the negative side no comments were specific to data and about 24% were negative specifying open publications. In both the positive and negative categories, the sub-code “financial” was relevant, with about 24% of negative comments falling here and 9% of positive comments.

Positive comments were also coded into the following topic-based categories: available or accessible (e.g., “raw data available to all for research”), collaboration or sharing (e.g., “sharing knowledge with all”), public engagement (e.g., “reliable knowledge for the public”), and trust or transparency (e.g., “integrity”).

The answers to the question “What is the biggest obstacle to making your data open?” were grouped into five categories and revealed that administrative barriers, security, and data issues are the main obstacles (Figure 4). Administrative barriers were pointed out to be company demands and secrets which discourage people; for security it was mainly the fear of being scooped, patents and confidentiality; and data issues were poor quality, imperfection, and not enough quantity. Other obstacles were mentioned such as lack of knowledge, lack of time and financial barriers. Together with the data issues, the last three obstacles clearly suggest a lack of understanding about open data: money is not necessary to open data as there are free repositories available such as Zenodo; the time required and the effort spent to open the data will decrease as people understand how to do it; poor quality and imperfect data may be true for one person but not for others; and the quantity of data does not limit uploading - in fact few data added to other open data will eventually make a big amount of data! Thus, these results suggest that the biggest obstacle to making data open is the lack of understanding, accounting for 50% of answers.

Figure 3. Full tree map of comments raised to the workshops 2021 and 2022 to the question “What comes to your mind with open science, open data, open publishing?” (n=125).

Figure 4. Identified obstacles to making data open displayed by categories (%) by participants of workshops 2021 and 2022.

In the final question addressing what participants already know about the topic, the participants were able to correctly name 12 correct open science repositories. The most common was Zenodo, followed by arXiv, and then figshare and GitHub (Figure 5). Showing a lack of open science knowledge, 28% of respondents named web search engines (e.g., Google Scholar), infrastructures (e.g., OpenAire, EOSC), publishers (e.g., Elsevier) and communities (e.g., Research Gate) as open science repositories.

In the second category of open-ended questions, participants addressed what they found important about the topic. Here they responded to what they would teach others about what they had just learned, and this resulted in 82 sentences. The most common words in their sentences were identified by a discourse analysis tool and used to produce a word cloud (Figure 6a) which shows: “open”, “data”, “sharing”, “access”, “upload”, “FAIR” and “Zenodo”. These words reflect the themes of the 2021 and 2022 workshops but also that the participants want to teach others about the values inherent in open science, shown in the three words, access, sharing and FAIR and exemplified by these sentences: “Open Science is good for all citizens as it allows **access** to all, even if you don't have an affiliation”; “Reach new horizons with data **sharing**”; “The scientific work should not be only open but also **FAIR**”.

Figure 5. Open repositories identified by participants of workshops in 2021 and 2022.

Figure 6. Participant comments from workshops 2021 and 2022 to the question “what do you teach others” represented in a word cloud (a) all comments considered, (b) comments repeated three times by different participants.

Words repeated more than 3 times were identified (Figure 6b) and in addition to the previous words, others were highlighted such as “science”, “research”, “licenses”, “repositories”, “easy”, “community”, “attractive”, “principles”, “metadata”, “readers”, “free” and “control”. This suggests

that participants not only want to teach the importance of open data to science, research and the community, but also teach about principles, licenses, repositories, metadata, how easy and safe it can be and the need to make it attractive: “**Community** work in **science** should be based in open **science** following FAIR **principles**”; “There are different types of open access **repositories**”; “**Metadata** importance for uploading in Zenodo”, “Zenodo is an **easy** and **free** platform to share **science**, choosing License and access you **control**”; “There are different **licenses**”.

At the workshop 2023, “A Researcher’s Journey through the FNSCloud”, participants did not answer any in-workshop questions due to time constraints, since this workshop was a presentation of the nascent FNS-Cloud and included hands-on activities on the FNS tools.

Post-Workshop Evaluation

The post-workshop evaluations were completed by 50% of participants. The evaluation had three Likert scale questions offering three to five options: “How would you rate the workshop overall?”, “My basic knowledge on Open Science/Uploading/FNS Cloud before the Workshop was satisfactory” and “My basic knowledge on Open Science/Uploading/FNS Cloud after the Workshop was satisfactory”; and 2 open-ended questions: “What was your favorite part of the workshop?” and “If you were to organize the next Workshop, what would you do differently?”.

The overall ratings of the 2021 and 2022 workshops were mostly very (52%) and extremely helpful (30%) while the 2023 workshop was rated very helpful by 80% of the participants (Figure 7). All the workshops reached a very good rate (80-90%) but while in the workshops 2021 and 2022, 30% of the participants rated them as excellent and 17% medium, in the workshop 2023 the medium (10%) and excellent (10%) rate decreased.

Figure 7. Participants rate the workshop overall.

When participants were asked if their basic knowledge on Open Science/Uploading/FNS Cloud was satisfactory before the workshop, it's clear that in all workshops the ones with satisfactory knowledge were in the same percentage (30%), yet the ones with no satisfactory knowledge were higher in the 2023 workshop and neutrals higher in the 2021 and 2022 workshops (Figure 8). However, the total percentage of neutrals and no satisfactory knowledge was similar in all the workshops (70%).

After the workshops, there were no neutrals and no satisfactory knowledge among the participants of Workshop 2023 and a residual percentage of not satisfactory (4%) and neutral (2%) in the workshops 2021 and 2022. These results explain the ones obtained for the overall rate: the decrease in the rates of “Somewhat helpful” and the increment of “very helpful” observed in the Workshop 2023 and the higher percentage of “Somewhat helpful” in the workshops 2021 and 2022.

The favorite parts of participants were the interactive activities and discussions, the comparisons made within the participants, the role-playing exercises, the hands-on activities, in particular the use of Zenodo platform as shown in the word cloud resulting from workshops 2021 and 2022 comments (Figure 9a). In the 2023 workshop the word Food stands out in the cloud, this is due to the type of activities specific related to food labeling and branded food, but the same words appeared in the cloud such as exercises, examples, discussion (Figure 9b).

Figure 8. Participants satisfaction on the knowledge on Open Science before and after the workshop.

Figure 9. Participant comments to the question “what was your favorite part of the workshop?” represented in a word cloud (a) workshops 2021 & 2022, (b) workshop 2023.

Participants also commented on the aspects that might be improved on the workshop 2021 such as exploring the basic knowledge and key concepts at the beginning, assigning participants to breakout groups based on previous knowledge, clearer discussion topics including more time for group exercises and more examples. In workshop 2022 the improvements were more related to exploring other platforms and metadata, and in workshop 2023 more practical work and explanation on the FAIRSPACE platform. This feedback reflected that participants in the end were motivated to learn more about open science and FNS-Cloud.

CONCLUSION

Researchers are willing to the new scientific system change in open science but the biggest obstacle they face is the lack of understanding which may be overcome with these interactive workshop series. Interactivity, discussions, role-playing exercises, hands-on activities were the success of these workshops found to be very and extremely helpful to gather knowledge on open science by most participants. In the end participants were motivated to learn more and to teach others about the values inherent in open science.

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Annex 1. Workshop Evaluation Questions

How would you rate the workshop overall? (Q1)

What is your professional area of expertise? (Q2)

My basic knowledge of Open Science/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS Cloud before the Workshop was satisfactory. (Q3)

My basic knowledge of Open Science/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS Cloud after the Workshop is satisfactory. (Q4)

I found the workshop length (2hr) (Q5)

What was your favorite part of the workshop? (Q6)

If you were to organize the next "Open Science Taster/Uploading Scientific Work/Using FNS Cloud" Workshop, what would you do differently? (Q7)

Thank you for taking the time to complete the survey. If you would like an FNS-Cloud certificate attesting to your completion of the workshop, please put your email in the box below. (Q8)